

LEARNING A LANGUAGE

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Abstract:

Learning a language is a complex process. It requires the teacher to be completely immersed in the process and have a personal approach to each student. Everyone has their weak points, but some principles are the same for everyone. There are points that must be present in any training of any person.

Key words: methodology, problems, effective method, totality, pedagogy, linguistics.

In order to learn a language you need to answer the following questions:

1. How to teach a language?

-The most important thing is vocabulary. It must be constantly updated, new words must be learned every day. Periodically give your students new words that you will use in the lesson: "Nature", so that it is easier for them to learn them:

nature, territory, mountains, flora, fauna, peak, valley, animals, plant, stem, leaves, spruce, fir tree, poplar, willow, canary, stork, crane, swallow, nightingale.

To make learning easier, use cards - a word in one language will be written on one side, and a word in another language on the other. You can also write sentences in Uzbek and translate into Russian:

1. I always eat on time;

2. Sport is the key to health;

3. Youth are our future.

2. How to build sentences in Russian?

-The next most important skill is the ability to speak and construct sentences. The ability to conduct a dialogue is equivalent to grammar, and these two directions are impossible without the other.

In order to competently combine these two areas, it is necessary that twenty percent of oral practice consist of repeating the grammar covered in the lesson: in phonetics: sounds, letters, syllables, stress; by morphology: one-part sentences, two-part sentences, common and uncommon sentences; simple sentence and complex sentence. And in order to compose complex sentences, you need to know conjunctions:

1. Connecting conjunctions: and; not only but ; Same; Also .

Dialogues with unions:

1. Today only boys play football?

- Today not only boys, but also girls play football.

2. Will it snow today?

-Today it will not only rain, but there will also be snow.

3. Has everyone left for Samarkand?

-Yes, I'll go get them now too.

2. Adversive conjunctions: but, but, then, even, however.

1. Has everyone come to class?

- Everyone came to class, but there was no lesson.

2. Did the doctor come into the clinic? -Yes, he went to the clinic, and there were no patients there.

3. Separating conjunctions: either, or...or, either...or, not that...not that.

1. Will dad come home today?

-Yes, he will come today, or he won't.

2. Is mom working from today?

- Yes, from today she works, or she doesn't work.

Subordinating conjunctions:

1. Temporary (indicate time): when, while, barely, only.

Was it dark when you returned home?

- Yes, when we returned home it was dark.

2. Causal (indicate the reason): because, since, because.

Why did you put on an old overcoat and an umbrella?

-Because it was raining.

3. Target (indicate the goal): in order (to), in order to, in order to.

Why did you leave the house?

-to give the land in Grenada to the peasants.

4. Conditional (indicate a condition): if, once, if.

How can you recognize a person?

-If you want to know a person, look at his friend.

5. Concessive (indicate the contradiction of one event to another): although; although; let him.

Was the gate locked?

-Although it was still early, the gates were locked.

Did you feel tired?

-None of us felt the slightest fatigue despite the fact that the hike had lasted for several days.

Will I live in songs?

Yes, let you die, but in the song of the brave and strong in spirit you will always be a living example, a call to the proud to freedom, to light.

6. Comparative (indicate comparison): as, as if, as if.

How did the cranes scream?

-The cranes flew quickly and quickly and screamed sadly, as if they were calling them to come with

them.

7. Investigative (indicate the investigation): so.

How is the wind in the hallway?

- In the entryway it was blowing from all sides, so that the candle almost went out.

8. Explanatory (indicate what they are talking about): what, so, as if.

What did you come to me with?

-I came to you with greetings, to tell you that the sun has risen, that it fluttered with hot light across the sheets.

You can test students with the game: “Who quickly corrects mistakes from the text?”

Text "My Motherland".

I think the Motherland is one of the greatest values in our lives. We do not choose which country we will be born into, but it is our moral duty to love and protect it in order to pass it on as an inheritance to our children. Firstly, the Motherland is not just the country in which you were born, but also the spiritual heritage of the people: language, culture, mentality, traditions and customs. (There are 7 errors in the text).

It is necessary to work on the errors:

Themselves, the greatest, the greatest, will pass on, in order to, in order to, gifts, property, to protect, to protect, bychay - customs.

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